

Experimental evaluation of soil-foam mixing under pressure for EPB tunneling

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Abstract

EPB TBM tunneling often relies upon the assumption of homogeneous conditioned soil in the tool gap of the cutterhead. Such a conditioned soil zone ensures that impermeability is maintained, that torque is lowered, and that the pressure from excavation chamber equilibrates in the tool gap, minimizing force on the cutterhead. Foam injection at the cutterhead occurs through a discrete number of ports, e.g., generally one port per 1-1.5 meter of cutterhead diameter. With such sparsely located ports, there is considerable reliance on the notion that the cutting tools and rotary action of the cutterhead serve to mix the soil and foam thoroughly. Given the remote and difficult access to the tool gap, it has been impossible to date to observe what is happening and whether there is homogeneous mixing of foam and soil in this area. More generally, the topic of soil-foam mixing has not been addressed in the literature, largely due to the complex experimental setup required to capture the mixing process. Research efforts on soil-foam mixing to date have been via numerical modeling approaches, e.g., computational fluid dynamics. Without experiments, however, these computational modeling results cannot be validated. This paper presents the results of an experimental program designed and conducted to examine foam injection and soil-foam mixing under pressure. A unique rotary action cylinder, with Plexiglas on one side, was developed to allow foam injection via stationary ports into a pressurized environment. Simultaneously, mixing tools are rotated through the soil specimen. The mixing behavior of foam and soil was examined via digital image analysis. A fluorescent green dye is introduced into the foam tank to create better contrast during imaging. This paper investigates the mechanism of soil-foam mixing as well as the influence of total pressure and number of the mixing tools on the degree of soil-foam mixing in the tool gap via image analysis technique. It was found that the mixing mechanism is governed by initiation of low and high-pressure zones behind and in front of the mixing tools. The results showed that an increase in total pressure leads to retarded mixing efficiency. It was also found that although more number of mixing tools yielded a higher mixing efficiency, the mixing patterns is alike. It implied that the excavation tools located farther out from the cutterhead center would mix the soil and foam efficiently even at the center favoring the fact that there is not as much tools on the cutterhead center due to limited space available.

Key word: soil conditioning, soil-foam mixing, experimental setup, tool gap

1. Introduction

EPB tunneling has successfully been adopted in recent years in very different ground conditions. The introduction of foam and polymers is a key reason for the increased application of this technology to many different types of soils. The soil is conditioned for multiple purposes: controlling the face pressure, minimizing the water inflow, promoting a homogenous flow of the excavated soil in the tool gap and through the excavation chamber and screw conveyor, minimizing the cutterhead and the screw conveyor torque, reducing the friction between the shield and the soil around, and minimizing tool wear.

EPB TBM tunneling relies upon the assumption of homogenous conditioned soil in the tool gap of the cutterhead, a region extending from the flat face of the cutterhead out to the tips of the cutting tools. In the tool gap, the soil scraped off the face via rotary action of the cutterhead is supposedly

conditioned thoroughly with the foam present at the face, i.e., the foam is delivered to the face through a discrete number of ports on the cutterhead during excavation. For a metro-size EPB TBM (6.5-7 m) there are generally 4-6 ports at the cutterhead face that deliver foam to the soil in the tool gap. The number of ports grows with TBM diameter. In order to have the soil in the tool gap conditioned, the foam ought to be uniformly dispersed throughout the scraped soil in this zone. In other words, the foam and soil have to be perfectly mixed via shearing and rotating actions of cutting tools and the cutterhead, respectively.

Despite that the importance of tool gap soil-foam mixing, the mechanics of mixing in the tool gap remain unknown in the literature mainly due to difficult access to the tool gap for visualization or sensing and lack of machine data or sampling from the tool gap. Laboratory-based reproduction of tool gap mixing is difficult as well. To the authors' knowledge, no research has been performed on soil-foam mixing in the tool gap to date.

Qualitative mixing characterization can provide insight into foam-soil mixing mechanics and effectiveness. The ability to characterize the mixing of granular materials has advanced quite rapidly over recent decades in other fields. This is mainly due to advances in noninvasive measurement techniques such as digital photography image analysis (Aït Aïssa et al., 2010; Busciglio et al., 2009; Daumann et al., 2009), particle image velocimetry (de Jong et al., 2012), and X-ray visualization (Uchida and Okamoto, 2008).

The aim of the present study is to characterize soil-foam mixing under pressure via laboratory experiments. An online monitoring of the surface texture evolution of the soil-foam mixture is developed through an experimental setup. A unique rotary action cylinder, with Plexiglas on one side, was developed, allowing for foam injection via stationary ports into a pressurized environment. This paper explores the mixing mechanism of soil and foam as well as the influence of total pressure and the number of the mixing tools on the mixing efficiency and patterns in the tool gap.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Experimental setup

A pressurized mixing chamber (PMC) was specifically designed to enable examination of soil-foam mixing by injecting foam via stationary ports into the pressurized environment while rotation of mixing tools occurs in the chamber. This rotary action cylinder permits visualization of soil-foam mixing through a Plexiglas plate shown in Figure (1). This Plexiglas plate houses two stationary foam ports at 38 mm and 64 mm radii. The mixing tools were mounted on a support plate and a central shaft, which transfers rotation to the mixing tools. Dimensions and position of the mixing tools are shown in Figure (1) & (2). The setup was then fastened on its side to a frame allowing for horizontal assessment of soil-foam mixing in the tool gap.

Figure 1 Pressurized mixing chamber (PMC, dimensions in mm). The parts of the PMC are as follows: a) reaction plate, compression spring, c) air release valve, d) top platen, e) mixing tools, f) Plexiglas plate, g) foam ports

Total vertical stress up to 4 bar is applied to the soil via calibrated load spring pushing against a movable top loading platen. The top platen is lowered onto the soil while recording its deformation. The compressed load spring provides a total vertical stress to the top of the soil sample σ_{vt} as:

$$\sigma_{vt} = \frac{(H_{S1} - H_{S2})k}{A} \quad (1)$$

Where H_{S1} and H_{S2} are the initial and final spring heights, k is the spring constant, and A is the area of the top platen and soil specimen. The height of the soil specimen is then determined to fulfill two purposes simultaneously: one is to reach desire total pressure in the chamber, and the other is to have the tips of the mixing tools flush with the Plexiglas plate. The latter ensures that the location of the mixing tools is known during experiment runs. Pore pressure was not measured and, therefore, effective stress is unknown.

Figure 2 PMC setup and the frame

A high-resolution camera horizontally aligned with the centerline of the mixing chamber, is placed in front of the Plexiglas plate to record the soil-foam mixing in time.

2.2 Material

The properties of the granular soil used in this study are listed in Table 1. Grain size distribution of the sand is presented in Figure (3).

Table 1 Properties of the used soil

Soil type	Poorly graded medium sand (SP)
Plasticity index (PI)	Non plastic
Moist density (g / cm³)	2.12
e_{max}	0.76
D₅₀ (mm)	0.76

Figure 3 Grain size distribution of the testing sand

A common industrial surfactant was used in a lab-scale foam generator to produce foam. The surfactant was diluted in water prior to foaming with a concentration of 5% by volume. The pore pressure dependent foam expansion ratio (FER_p) and foam injection ratio (FIR_p) are determined by the liquid and air flow meters of the foam generator using equations shown below (Mori et al., 2015).

$$FER_0 = \frac{V_{Foam}}{V_{Solution}} = \frac{V_{Air} + V_{Solution}}{V_{Solution}} \quad (1)$$

$$FIR_0 = \frac{V_{Foam}}{V_{Soil}} \quad (2)$$

$$FER_p = 1 + (FER_0 - 1) \frac{P_{atm}}{P_{atm} + P} \quad (3)$$

$$FIR_p = FIR_0 \frac{FER_p}{FER_0} \quad (4)$$

Where p is the air gage pressure. All pressures reported in this paper are gage pressure. Subscript $p = 0$ represents atmospheric or zero gage pressure.

In this paper, FER_p and FIR_p are maintained at 10 and 50% respectively. Using equations 1 to 4, soil-conditioning parameters used for various mixing tests are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 Soil conditioning parameters used for mixing tests at various pressures

p (bar)	FER_0	FIR_0 (%)	FER_p	FIR_p (%)
0	10	50	10	50
1	19	95	10	50
2	28	140	10	50

Mixing experiments are based on pronounced color contrast for the use of image analysis techniques. To serve this purpose, the foam is dyed by adding a certain concentration of water-based green fluorescent powder to the foaming tank. The foam is then excited by long-wavelength ultraviolet lights, which are positioned all around the mixing setup to illuminate the injected foam on the surface of the Plexiglas plate. The clear Plexiglas plate is machined out of ultraviolet-transmitting material to allow the ultraviolet (UV) light to excite the fluorescent foam.

2.3 Image analysis for soil-foam mixing evaluation

A limited time of 6 minutes is set for each experiment in which TIFF images with resolution of 4288×2848 pixels were recorded every 20 seconds. A digital color camera is placed in a tripod in front of the mixing chamber and a black screen is placed behind the chamber to allow simple contour detection. For image processing, a 7×7 median filter is first applied to even out background variations and enhance the images. The images are then segmented into black being the soil grains and white being the dyed foam. Figure 4 shows the segmentation process along with the original images. Let {Mixed (M), Unmixed (UM)} be the set of two classes of white and black corresponding to the regions of interest in the mixing chamber, i.e., to represent soil-foam mixture and soil grain only, respectively. These classes are determined by considering the color evolution of the mixing process in the mixing chamber going from dark grey (color of soil particles) to bright green (color of dyed foam). In this case, the bright green defines the mixed regions while dark grey defines the unmixed regions (Melton et al., 2002). Let $f(x, y)$ be the function representing a RGB image, where the value of this function at each point is defined by a three-dimensional vector, $f(x, y) = (R(x, y), G(x, y), B(x, y))$.

Let $p(x_i, y_i) \in f(x, y)$, the classification of $p(x_i, y_i)$ in the sets of mixed pixels (M) or unmixed pixels (UM) be defined as follows:

$$p(x_i, y_i) = \begin{cases} M & \text{if } \text{bright green} \\ UM & \text{if } \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Although there are numerous indices for mixing quantification, a straightforward mixing index is used as follow (Nalesso et al., 2015):

$$\text{Mixing Index}(MI) = \frac{M}{M + UM} \quad (6)$$

Figure 4 binarization of images, (a1-3) original images (b1-3) binarized images

2.4 Experimental procedure

For each test, dry soil is first brought to in-situ saturation assuming a density of 2.09 g/cm³ by adding 19.5% water by weight. The PMC is filled with various height of saturated soil sample depending upon, first, the target total pressure for tests and, second, upon the notion of having the mixing tools tip flush with the Plexiglas plate, i.e., 25, 31, and 36 mm of saturated soil to reach atmospheric, 1, and 2 bar of total pressure. Therefore, it is ensured that no soil layer exists beyond the reach of the mixing tools while the desired total pressure is maintained.

The top platen, with a central hole to house the shaft connecting and transferring rotary motion to the mixing tools, is placed on top of the soil. An air release port in the top platen is plugged up and the spring and the load reaction plate are positioned. The soil is then pressurized by lowering the reaction plate in prescribed increments to compress the calibrated load spring. Spring compression can be measured at each increment and the applied vertical force is calculated from this multiplied by the spring constant.

The PMC is then fixed into a steel frame horizontally by clamping down on the chamber wall shown in Figure 2. With the camera locked in the tripod looking into the Plexiglas plate along with UV light posts positioned around the chamber, dyed foam is injected into the chamber through one of the foam ports tapped on the Plexiglas plate to reach the desire FIR (Table 2) depending upon the total pressure in the mixing chamber. The central shaft is then turned at a constant rotational speed of 3 RPM. The camera is programmed to shoot after each complete rotation of the mixing tools (every 20 seconds). For each test, the images taken are then stored in a desktop computer for further image analysis. This

paper investigates the influence of total pressure and number of tools on the mixing characteristics of soil and foam..

3. Results

3.1 relationship between total pressure and mixing behavior

Three mixing tests were performed under zero, one and two bar total pressure to investigate the effect of total pressure on mixing behavior in the tool gap presented in Figure 5. However, the pore water pressure and void ratio were not recorded in these tests.

Figure 5 Mixing behavior under various pressures with 3 RPM rotational speed

The influence of total pressure on soil-foam mixing provokes various mixing patterns shown in Figure 5. While under atmospheric condition, the foam merely pursues circumferential trajectories of mixing tools. As the tools rotate, low and high-pressure zones are generated behind and head of the tools, respectively. The foam flows into the low-pressure zone and therefore follows the tool trajectory whilst it is pushed out once in front of the tools (high-pressure zone) towards the center. These low and high-pressure zones continues to exist as long as the mixing tools are rotating; the continuous formation of these zones accounts for concentric circular mixing pattern observed under atmospheric pressure despite number of the tools.

Figure 6 demonstrates the high-pressure zones highlighted with yellow outline along with trajectories of the mixing tools. The foam not only flows behind the tool trajectories, but it also runs towards the center of the chamber; this is due to the soil network being sheared circumferentially. With the total pressure increasing from zero to two bar, the foam develops a curly motion towards the center of the chamber.

Figure 6 low and high-pressure zones near the mixing tools after $\frac{1}{4}$ turn

One possible explanation is that the pressure promotes chains of interlocked grains (notion of effective stress) and, on the other hand, suppresses the dilation phenomenon of soil grains as the mixing tools pass through, which was more pronounced during tests under atmospheric condition. The shearing action of the mixing tools is transmitted to the center due to high grain-to-grain pressure creating a pathway for the foam to flow. Besides, the mixing tools compact the soil beyond their reach (towards the wall of the chamber) such that the foam cannot penetrate and ultimately mixes with soil.

Figure 7 shows the mixing index as a function of mixing tool revolutions for each of the three pressures. In each test, the mixing index increases linearly and plateaus after approximately 8 revolutions. Thereafter, little additional mixing occurs. Figure 7 shows that 60-70% mixing is achieved at the plateau point. Total pressure has only a small influence on mixing index, with higher pressure slightly retarding the mixing. In the end, the achieved mixing index is independent of pressure.

Figure 7 Mixing efficiency for various pressure under constant 3 RPM rotational speed

Knowing that the foam tends to curl in towards the center of the mixing chamber and the notion of mixing time (Figure 5 and 7), it is safe to say that the foam injected into the face through the ports located far from the cutterhead center remains longer in the tool gap. Therefore, the foam travels a longer radial distance towards the cutterhead center increasing the time available for the foam to be mixed with the scraped soil in the tool gap. Besides, this concentric curly motion of the foam towards the cutterhead center atones for lower linear speed at the center. Nevertheless, it requires further investigation into latter conclusion.

3.2 Relationship between the number of tools and mixing behavior

The mixing tool with a shorter radius on the mixing support plate (shown in Figure 2) is removed for all tests presented here; the mixing tests are carried out using one mixing tool with their results shown in Figure 8. Direction of rotation is counterclockwise and gravity is acting downward. Here, the foam only follows the circumferential low-pressure zones created behind the only mixing tool and, after 3 revolutions, it starts to curl in towards the center of the chamber. Unlike the mixing patterns (shown in Figure 5) with 2 mixing tools, the mixing does not occur uniformly across the face of the chamber and it takes longer to achieve the same mixing index as to when there was two mixing tools.

Figure 8 Mixing behavior with one mixing tool under various pressures

Figure 9 presents the analogy of mixing indices for one versus two mixing tools under different total pressure conditions. Here, it is clear that two tools promote faster mixing, though not proportionally. Besides, as the total pressure increases, the significance of number of the mixing tools becomes even more conspicuous as shown in Figure 9a-c. It implies that the working pressure is one of the decisive factors in determination of number of the tools on the cutterhead, if mixing efficiency in the tool gap is of a priority.

Figure 9 Mixing efficiency for one and two tools under various total pressure condition a) 0 bar b) 1 bar c) 2 bar d) mixing with one tool under different total pressure condition

By comparing mixing patterns presented in Figure 5 (mixing with two tools) and Figure 8 (Mixing with 1 tool), it is perceived that foam travels towards the center of the face regardless of the number of tools, meaning that the mixing index achieved ultimately is the same. It is known that the center of the cutterhead provides limited space for excavation tools due to heavy structure required to house the tools (Grothen, 2015). Instead, by adding tools on the outer perimeter of the cutterhead, the overall mixing efficiency in the tool gap is enhanced suggested by the results presented in Figure 5 and 8. This ends up working well in relationship to the limited space available at the center of the cutterhead for tool installation.

It is worth noting that the mixing index is likely a function of a number of parameters that cannot be explored in a single conference paper. The number of mixing tools as well as the geometry of the setup, e.g., radius of each tool and area of tool path in proportion to total area. Further, the two tools used here acted independently because they were more than 10 diameters apart. The cooperative influence of combined tools was not examined.

Conclusion

A unique rotary mixing chamber was used to examine mixing behavior of soil and foam. Two series of tests were performed varying the number of mixing tools and total pressure in the mixing chamber. It was found that the soil-foam mixing mechanism in the tool gap is the formation of low and high-pressure zones behind and in front of the mixing tools in the mixing chamber. The foam is pulled into the low-pressure zones outlining a circumferential trajectory as the tools spin.

Results showed that the total pressure lower the mixing efficiency requiring longer time to achieve a well-mixed conditioned soil in the tool gap. This was attributed to a stronger grain-to-grain contact among soil particles making it harder for the mixing tools to promote connections among the voids.

The number of the mixing tools was found to influence both the mixing pattern and efficiency of soil and foam in the tool gap. Nonetheless, the foam circled in towards the center of the mixing chamber, which was more prominent when only one tool was used. This behavior suggested that excavation tools installed away from the cutterhead center and towards the perimeter, not only would mix the soil and foam on their tracks, but also would direct the foam towards the center of the cutterhead. This favors the notion of less tools available near the cutterhead center.

While not a scaled model of a TBM cutterhead, the rotary mixing chamber was developed to provide insight into tool gap mixing. The application and extension of these limited results to cutterhead tool gap mixing are premature but will come with further test results.

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